

Women's Access and Rights to Land and implications for Food Security in Ondo State, Nigeria

Mayowa O. SOBOWALE

Department of Research Outreach

Cocoa Research Institute of Nigeria (Research Scientist)

E-mail: mayowadamy5@gmail.com

Modupe Oziofu ALA

Department of Sociology,

Lead City University (Lecturer)

E-mail: ebunala@yahoo.com

Abstract

One of the strategies to boost women's production in agriculture is through access to productive resources. The study investigated the implications of women's access and rights to land on household's food security in Ondo State, Nigeria. The study adopted a survey research design, using primary data. A multistage random sampling procedure was used to select 120 respondents from Akure North and Akure South Local Government Areas of Ondo State. Descriptive statistics (frequency counts, percentages and mean) and inferential statistics (Chi-square and Pearson Product Moment Correlation, PPMC) were used in analysis. The findings of the study showed that most of the respondents were relatively young with a mean age of 45 years. A high proportion (80%) of the respondents were literate, most of which were married (73.63%) with a moderate family size of five persons per household and were involved in all the religious practices in the area. Although (80%) of the respondents had access and rights to land, which they acquire mostly through inheritance, the farmlands of most (70%) was less than one hectare, with an average annual income below ₦100,000 per annum. It is perceived that access to land would enhance early crop planting, crop diversification, food security and improve women's livelihood. Also, access to land positively affected the crops planted, food availability but have no effect on food security and income. The study recommends increase in farm size, engagement in value addition and training programs to improve food security and income of women farmers in the area.

Keywords: Access to land, right to land & Food security.

Introduction:

Access to land is a critical factor influencing agricultural productivity and food security, especially in rural households of developing countries. In many African societies, including Nigeria, agriculture serves as a primary livelihood source, with women playing a significant role in food production, processing, and marketing. Despite their contributions, women's access to productive resources like land remains limited due to cultural, legal, and institutional barriers. This restriction hampers their capacity to enhance agricultural output, diversify income, and improve household food security. Lands remain a means of security against poverty in developing countries, but gender discrimination and inequalities put women at a disadvantage. Women access to land is limited. In most traditions, women do not inherit land. Rights to land are given to male children or other members of the household. However, the

case is different in Akure North and Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo- State. Female children are opportune to access land and its properties from their parents. But one wonders if the access and rights to land of the women in Akure North and Akure South affects their food security status.

This study examines the relationship between women's access to land and household food security in Ondo State, Nigeria. It investigates the socio-demographic factors affecting women's land access, the methods of land acquisition, and the impact of land ownership on agricultural productivity and household food security. The objective of the study is to ascertain women access to land, to examine the rights of women to land and to investigate the perceived effect of women access to land and household food security in the study area. The findings aim to inform policies and programs that promote gender equity in land access and agricultural development.

Background of the Study

Rural areas are areas located outside towns and cities within the country. It is an open swath of land with few homes and buildings. Chigbu, (2013) cited by Abdulwakeel, (2017) adds to this, that fewer people reside in the rural areas with their homes and businesses located far away from each other. While agriculture remains the primary occupation of rural dwellers, the majority of them live and work on farms or ranches and are also surrounded by villages, towns, hamlets, and other small settlements. Wildlife is found more frequently in rural areas more than the urban centers because of the absence of people and buildings. Even though the population density of rural areas is lower compared to urban areas, poverty is more in rural areas than urban areas, despite that rural women are the major food provider and food security agents.

Aziz, Ren, Rong, & Zhou (2021) opine that whenever women's access to productive resources (such as land) is enhanced, agricultural output would be increased by as much as 2.5% to 4%. As a result of this, more food, up to 30% would be provided by women for their household, which will give room for adequate feeding, food availability, and better health. In rural communities, land is valuable, and at times the only asset. Women's access to land in the rural areas gives them greater opportunity for empowerment, improves their standard of living, gives them access to credit facilities for other projects and serves to support the family. Most people (including women) living in rural areas are informal workers, with limited or no access to social protection. Women play a crucial role in creating a good atmosphere, continuity of rural households and communities, thereby improving their general wellbeing and improve their livelihood within the rural areas. Women in the rural areas perform the bulk of domestic work and unpaid care within families and rural households. Despite their significant role in the agricultural sector, women in the rural area find themselves in disadvantaged position compared to men in the same community. They are often faced with more restricted access to assets, financial resources, and social protection. Women and girls living in rural areas lack access to public services such as good education, portable water, comprehensive health care, infrastructure, and productive resources. The patriarchal politics played out in rural households, the gender-biased social norms, customary laws, and practices are some of the determinants of women's access and rights to land in the rural community. Most of the women in the rural areas are always faced with formal and informal barriers depriving them of rights and access to owning land. Globally, women in rural areas play a crucial role in agriculture, land and natural resources management, rural enterprises, food security, and nutrition.

Food is a fundamental need of all living creatures; man can live without clothing and shelter but cannot exist without food. Food security is a phenomenon that has been a global

issue of major concern, especially in the developing world. This is because, it has been considered as a template for ensuring a good society and economy (Appendini and Quijada, 2016). Food securities do not only affect human health and well-being, but they also contribute to political instabilities in some countries where they are facing food insecurity challenges. Food security is a multi-dimensional phenomenon starting from the global to the individual level and its determinant which includes civil conflicts, social norms, natural disaster, and climate change also differs at different levels.

Despite all the rich agricultural resources Nigeria is endowed with, food insecurity remains one of her major challenges, even as her populations continue to grow daily and with a projection of 258 million people by 2030. Women and children are the most defenseless to food insecurity and hunger. According to Callister (2018), women and girls suffer greatly in the world and over 60% of women and girls are underfed and undernourished. This affects the reproductive cycle of the woman and the girl child. Babies given birth to by malnourished mothers are found with cases of low birth weights (LBW). LBW is one of the strongest indicators which foretell the likelihood of a child's death before his or her fifth birthday (Ntenda, 2019). In some cultures, despite women's involvement in food preparation and production, they are not expected to eat until after other members of the family have taken the better part of the meal. Whenever there are food shortages, family crises such as battering and divorce are always on increase, while women and youngsters are left to defend themselves, particularly in societies where shunning of divorced women is entrenched in their culture. Of course, young girls with early marriages are also caught up in this web. Females with early marriage are more likely to end their education early, become pregnant early, become malnourished, die during childbirth, and give birth to babies with a poor health condition (Save The Children, 2014), (Kabir, Ghosh, & Shawly, 2019). Female-headed households are usually exposed to this condition. Some of them do not have access to economic resources like land, financial services, and training in livelihood skills which are needed to improve their food security. They also lack the legal power to claim the resources they do have access to and rights to Gavrilovic, Koechlein, Kaaria, & Winder-Rossi, (2018). According to Daramola, Adebo, & Adebo (2016), women play a major role in agricultural production, food processing, and marketing. Women are deeply involved in food production activities beginning from weeding, bush burning, hoeing, planting, harvesting, threshing, bagging, carrying/ transportation, and usage. Women's involvement in food production can neither be measured nor quantified, because they play dual role of unpaid workers on family farms and as paid or unpaid laborers on other farms and agricultural enterprises. Be it at the commercial or subsistence levels, they are always involved in both crop and livestock production. Some of them produce food and cash crops and they are seen managing mixed agricultural operations that involve crops, livestock, and fish farming. All of these makes women important and valued asset in the agricultural labor force and food production. In most of the developing countries, women produce a larger percentage (60-80%) of their food crops seeds. (Arene and Anyaeji, 2010), (Achterbosch, Berkum and Meijerink, 2014), (Doss, 2014).

Irrespective of gender, people are empowered and benefit from development policies and practices that improve nutrition and food security when there is a deliberate gender approach to food security (SIDA, 2015). All humans deserve the rights to sufficient food, but oftentimes, and in many instances, women and girl child had always been at the receiving end of food shortages and scarcity in society, just because they are denied basic human rights like access to quality education, good and standard health care facility, a good and decent job, and the right to own property.

Literature Review:

The conceptual framework of this study focuses on the relationship between women's access to land and household food security. It considers key components such as socio-demographic factors (age, education, household size), land acquisition methods (inheritance, purchase), and land utilization (size, quality, tenure). These factors affect agricultural productivity, income, and, ultimately, household food security. The framework suggests that while land access can indirectly improve food security, its impact is mediated by factors like farm size, income, and external support.

The theoretical framework of the study is based on the Sustainable Livelihood Framework (SLF) and the Resource-Based Theory (RBT). The SLF highlights the importance of access to resources, like land, in achieving sustainable livelihoods, while the RBT emphasizes how resource ownership, such as land, enhances productivity and competitiveness. Together, they underline how women's access to land can influence agricultural productivity, income generation, and food security.

Finally, the empirical framework operationalizes the relationships between the measurable variables, applying econometric models and using qualitative and quantitative methods to test the proposed linkages.

The accessibility and rights of women to land have been extensively studied, particularly for their significance in securing rural household food availability and sustenance. Numerous studies highlight the challenges women face in accessing land and its implications for food and land security. For instance, Meinzen-Dick et al. (2019) explored women's rights to land as a means of poverty alleviation through empirical reviews of existing data. Their findings highlighted strong associations between women's land rights and improved decision-making in consumption, enhanced bargaining power, and greater investment in human capital. However, associations with other factors, such as livelihoods and agricultural productivity, were weaker. This underscores the need to address systemic barriers that limit the broader impact of women's land rights.

Shaffer (2019) further examined barriers to women's access to land and their implications for empowerment and livelihood improvement. Analyzing data from interviews, Shaffer found that legal standards, such as the 2010 constitution, have not fully dismantled gender biases. Women continue to face systemic denial of land rights due to entrenched patriarchal attitudes. The study recommended community campaigns, investment in mediation efforts, and legal reforms to address these challenges. This aligns with findings from Zhou et al. (2019), who investigated food security in Pakistan's northern hinterlands. The study revealed that gender plays a pivotal role in food insecurity, with female-led households disproportionately affected. The authors called for targeted policies to address the vulnerabilities of female-led families, emphasizing education and empowerment initiatives.

Issoufou et al. (2020) studied women's accessibility to land in Zinder and Maradi regions of Niger, highlighting the constraints posed by social and cultural beliefs. Communal approaches to landownership often limit women's ability to gain legitimate control over land. The study underscored the need for statutory authorities to legitimize women's land rights and dismantle cultural barriers. Similarly, Westholm and Ostwald (2020) reviewed food production and land use across Latin America, Africa, and Asia, focusing on multi-faceted land utilization systems. Their findings revealed a scarcity of literature on using land for diverse functions to

enhance empowerment and food security. Women's agricultural products often face market access barriers, relegating them in decision-making processes.

Finally, Lokonon and Pilo (2021) investigated the relationship between women's land access and food security in Benin, analyzing data from a 2013 survey. Their results showed a positive correlation between women's land control and household food consumption scores, with women farmers who had access to and control over land achieving better food consumption grades. This underscores the critical role of women's land rights in improving dietary diversity and food security.

The reviewed literature collectively demonstrates that women's access to land is integral to their empowerment and the broader goal of food security. While studies have revealed varying challenges across regions, common themes such as systemic discrimination, socio-cultural constraints, and inadequate policy frameworks highlight the urgent need for reforms. Moving forward, targeted interventions addressing these barriers will be crucial in enhancing women's rights to land, fostering empowerment, and achieving sustainable food security outcomes.

Materials and Method

The study adopted a survey research design. It employed the use of primary data. The population of the study consists of all women of different categories that are indigenes and living within Akure North and South Local Government Areas (LGA) of Ondo state.

A multi-stage sampling procedure was used for the study. The first stage involves a purposive selection of two Local Government Areas (Akure North and South LGA) of Ondo state. The two LGAs were purposively selected due to the equal rights accorded both male and female descendants in the area. The second stage involves a random selection of six communities from each of the LGA. The third stage involves a snowball selection of ten respondents from each community, thus making a total sample size of one hundred and twenty respondents.

The data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics involve the use of frequency counts and percentages while the inferential statistics involved the use of Pearson Product Moment correlation (PPMC) and Chi-square. The PPMC was used to measure the strength and direction of the relationship between women's access to land and their household food security levels and the size of land owned by women and agricultural productivity in Ondo State, Nigeria.

$$r = \frac{\sum (x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y - \bar{y})^2}}$$

r = Correlation coefficient

x = Independent variable (e.g., women's land access)

y = Dependent variable (e.g., food security level)

\bar{x} = Mean of X

\bar{y} = Mean of Y

While the Chi-Square test was used to examine the association between women's land ownership status (Yes/No) and their level of food security (Secure/Insecure) and the significant difference in food security between women with and without land rights

$$X^2 = \sum (O - E)^2 / E$$

O = Observed frequency

E = Expected frequency

VARIABLE	DESCRIPTION	TYPE OF VARIABLE	MEASUREMENT SCALE	INDICATORS
Women's access to land	The extent to which women have access to land for agricultural or other purposes	Independent	Categorical (Yes /No)	Ownership status, leasehold, inheritance right
Land size	The amount of land (in hectares) owned or accessed by women	Independent	Continuous	Size of land (measured in hectares or acres)
Food security status	The ability of households to access sufficient nutritious food	Dependent	Ordinal (food secure / mildly insecure / moderately insecure / severely insecure)	Household food insecurity access scale (HFIAS)
Education Level	The highest level of formal education attained by women	Control	Ordinal (No education/ Primary / Secondary /Higher)	Years of schooling
Age of respondents	The age of women participating in the study	Control	Continuous	Age in years
Marital status	Women's marital condition, which may affect land access	Control	Categorical (single / married / divorced / widowed)	Marital status classification

Results and Discussion

Socio-Economic characteristics of the respondents

The socio-economic characteristics of the respondents which include age, sex, marital status, family size, religion, primary and secondary occupation are wrapped up in Table 1 and 2 below: The result shows that 37.50% and 29.15% of the respondents were within the age range of 31-40 and 41-50 years respectively. The mean age of the respondents was 45years. It implies that the majority of the women in the study area are still young and are expected to be agile enough to embark on food production activities to meet their food needs.

The finding affirmed the assertion of Barau and Oladeji (2017) that most of the women who participate in farming exercises are in their active age and this might constantly improve and multiply their efficiency in agricultural production.

In the same vein, the study also disclosed that a preponderance (73.63 %) of the respondents were married while 11.70, 5.80, and 5.00% of the respondents were widowed, separated, and divorced respectively. The high percentage of the respondents that were married suggests a high level of responsibility and demand in meeting the family's needs. Married women are supposed to have access to the land for food production. The proportion of widows separated and divorced women might have challenges in accessing agricultural lands. According to World Bank (2018), widows and divorced women were marginalized, shunned, excluded, and divest of access to land in Nigeria.

A critical look into the family size of the respondents reveals that 68% of the respondents had 4-6 members in their households, 35% had between 1-3 persons in their households while 17% had between 7-9 people in their household. The mean family size of the respondents was five (5) people. The study shows that the respondents have moderate household sizes. The moderate household size might influence their capacity to meet the food needs of the family. This might also go a long way to affect their food security status as they will not spend the bulk of their earnings on meeting the basic needs of people at home. This is in accordance with the findings of Barau and Oladeji (2017) where a preponderance of the family size was six and above. Thus, concluded that clans with big sizes might enjoy the benefit of kinsmen labor to do more work on the farm.

Furthermore, the study shows that 17.50%, 40.0%, and 22.45%, of the respondents, had primary, secondary and tertiary education respectively, while 10.85% did not have any formal education at all. About 80.0% of the respondents are educated. It shows that majority of the respondents are learned. The high level of literacy of the respondents is expected to influence their knowledge on their rights to land and use the opportunity to claim their rights and access land for their food production. This agreed with Edet, Udoh, Sunday, Akpan & Edikan (2017) that the years of formal education have great significance on family competence to cope with reasonable livelihood capacity.

In addition, 73.33 percent of the respondents were Christians, 15.83 percent of the respondents were Muslim, while 10.83 percent of the respondents practiced the African traditional religion. It shows that the respondents were involved in all the religious practices that are being carried out in the area, although there were more Christians than those involved in other religions. The high proportion of Christians in the study area might influence their participation in farm works. This is because ladies, girls, and women who are Christian are not restricted from participating in agricultural activities, unlike their Muslim counterparts who for instance are banned by PUDAH from participating in several activities.

According to USAID (2015), Wealthy Muslim ladies, girls, and women in isolation do not participate in farming activities, but indigent Muslim women are heavily involved in all aspects of food production and preparation especially those working in rural areas. This further corroborates the assertion of Ogunlela and Mukhtar (2009), that religion can also influence women's participation in farming activities. Hausa and Fulani communities in Nigeria believed that women do not have to work in the field due to the restrictions imposed by religion and culture.

The study also captured the primary occupation of the respondents and disclosed that 60.83% of the respondents were farmers, 15.0% were civil servants, 14.17 % were traders, while 8.3% of the respondents were Artisans. Artisans generally include hairstylists, tailoring, chemists, cloth weaving, and catering services. It could be affirmed that most of the respondents' primary occupation is agriculture. The result is in line with the assertion of Otekhile and Verter (2017) that farming activities remain the main source of existence for the

rural dwellers in Nigeria. Udoh, Akpan, & Uko (2017) further confirmed that the generality of the rural households earned their living from agriculture. To achieve these, women require good and fertile soil with a favorable atmosphere to perform maximally. Access to land means fair allocation, prolonged use and expansion of the land resources.

While digging into their secondary occupation the study revealed that trading with 42.70% is the secondary vocation of the respondents in the study area, while farming activity still ranked high with 31.25% more than people who are artisans of 22.92% in the study area. It could be affirmed that the bulk of the women operating in the rural areas where the study was carried out engaged in non-farming activities like trading and artisan works. Ibidapo, Oso, and Ogunsipe (2017) affirmed that non-farm activities have become building block strategies for farmers living in the rural areas of developing countries.

Table 1: Distribution of the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents

Variables	Frequency (120)	Percentage
Age (Years)		
Less than 30	7	5.90
31 - 40	45	37.50
41 - 50	35	29.15
51 - 60	23	19.16
Above 60	10	8.35
Mean		45
Marital Status		
Single	5	4.20
Married	88	73.63
Separated	7	5.80
Divorced	6	5.00
Widowed	14	11.70
Household Size		
1-3	33	26.67
4-6	65	54.17
7-9	17	14.16
Above 10	5	4.17
Education Status		
Primary	21	17.50
Secondary	48	40.00
Tertiary	27	22.45
No-Formal Education	13	10.85
Non- Formal Education	11	9.15
Religion		
Christians	88	73.33
Muslim	19	15.83
African Traditional Religion	13	10.83
Primary Occupation		
Civil Servant	18	15.00
Farmers	73	60.83
Artisan	10	8.33
Traders	17	14.17

Daily wage labor	2	1.70
Others.	-	-
Secondary education		
Trading	41	42.70
Farming	30	31.25
Artisan	22	22.92
Others	3	3.13

Source: Field survey, 2019

Crops Planted by the Respondents

Figure 1 shows that all the respondents (100%) planted cassava and maize, while 84.17%, 72.50%, 70.83%, and 66.67% planted vegetables, yam, cocoyam, and melon respectively. Since all the respondents are women, we can refer to the under-listed planted crops as women's crops. FAO (2016), Kaaria, Osorio, Wagner, & Gallina (2016) established that women's crops are crops grown by women for home consumption rather than for sales. This result authenticates the findings of Agugo, Onuador, Okere, Uchegbulem, & Iheme, G. O. (2017) that female farmers who live in the local area grow staple crops like cassava (*Manihot esculenta*), diverse species of cocoyam (*Colocasia*), vegetables (pumpkin, sent leave, garden egg, bitter leaf, amaranths, etc.) as well as the rearing of animals e.g. poultry, goats and sheep. Their farming pattern also varies from small vegetable gardens behind the house to the cultivation of big farms with the high-density area far away from homes.

Fig 1: Crops planted by the respondents

Source: Field survey, 2019.

Access to Land

The result in Table 2 revealed that 80.1% of the respondents confirmed that they have access to land, while 19.9% of the respondents didn't have access to land in the study area. This access to land is expected to be one of the leading factors that endear their agricultural activities and have a positive impact on their means of existence. This result attests to the assertion of Isaac, Omowunmi, and Ayodeji (2019) that women's access to land determines and influences their livelihood and food security in Nigeria. The access to the land of most women in Akure South and Akure North Local Government Area is contrary to what operates in other parts of Nigeria, where women are denied access to land.

Table 2: Distribution of access to Land by the respondents

Access to Land	Frequency	%
Yes	96	80.10
No	24	19.90
Total	120	100.00

Source: Field survey, 2019.

Rights to Land.

The result in Figure 2 reveals that 67.5% of the respondents have rights to land while 32.5% of the respondents declined. Their land rights are expected to increase their standard of living and form a platform for poverty reduction and community development. It is also expected to improve their self-esteem and skill development. Once they can secure their land rights, the number of crops produced will increase; give women access to credit facilities

The women's right to land in the study area is affirmed by the UN Habitat (2006) that Women's rights to own and control land, is formally acknowledged under international law. However, the patriarchal system, traditions, policies, and discriminatory laws which persist in various countries are some of the obstacles which hinder women from enjoying their rights. Furthermore, this had also negated the previous opinions and assertion of FAO (2017) that most of the land cultivated by women are owned by men, and sometimes when they become the real owner, they may not have access to it, neither will they be able to control its usage because of cultural tradition and norms existing in those areas.

Fig 2: Rights to land by the respondents

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

Hypothesis Testing

H01: There is no relationship between the socioeconomic characteristics of the women and their access to land

All the socioeconomic characteristics tested were found to be significantly related to women access to land namely: age ($P = 0.000$), household size ($P = 0.002$), education ($P = 0.000$), and religion ($P = 0.001$). Since the interactive variables (access to land and age of the woman) are positive, the result suggests that as women advance in age their accessibility increases. This is expected as most of them gained land access through inheritance. In which case, when the parents are still alive, such a right would not be available. The positive and significant relationship that exists between household size and access to land might emanate from the possibility of the respondents using family members as source of labour on the farm. This will enable them to produce and earn more from farm sales. The positive and significant relationship between the level of education and land access might emanate from the fact that most of them are literate. Women that are literate are always conscious of their rights and might not be manipulated on land issues. Also, the significant and positive relationship between the religion and land access might emanate from the fact that most of the respondents were Christians and were not barred to work based on religion. This finding is in line with George, Olokoyo, Osabuohien, Efobi, and Becroft (2015) that certain socioeconomic empowers women and improves their livelihood.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study concludes that most of the women in Akure North and Akure South Local Government of Ondo State were young, married and literate. They have access and rights to

land. They planted a wide range of crops from cassava to yam, vegetables, maize and cocoyam. They are mostly small-scale farmers with most of them earning less than 2 dollars per day. The women farmers perceived that access to land would affect their early planting, crop diversification, food security, improve their livelihood and income. There is a positive and significant relationship between age, household size, education, religion and access to land by the respondents. Access to land positively affects crops planted and food availability of the respondents, hence the recommendations below.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- Training programs should be organised for women farmers on how to make effective use of their small lands to improve their food security and income status.
- Women should be encouraged to enhance their income by engaging in value addition activities.
- Women farmers should be encouraged to increase their farm size to medium or large-scale farming through improved access to virtually interest-free facilities. This will boost their productivity.
- Access and rights to land by women in other parts of Nigeria should be enhanced through favourable land policies.

References

Abdulwakeel, S. (2017). What is rurality? *Livelihood and Conflict View Project*.

Achterbosch, T. J., Berkum, S., Meijerink, G. W., Asbreuk, H., & Oudendag, D. A. (2014). *Cash crops and food security: Contributions to income, livelihood risk and agricultural innovation* (No. 2014-15). LEI Wageningen UR.

Appendini, K., & Quijada, M. G. (2016). Consumption strategies in Mexican rural households: pursuing food security with quality. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 33(2), 439-454.

Arene, C. J., & Anyaeji, R. C. (2010). Determinants of food security among households in Nsukka Metropolis of Enugu State, Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, 30(1), 9-16.

Asghar, Z. & Ahmed, M. (2013). Socio-Economic Determinants of Household Food Insecurity in Pakistan.

Aziz, N., Ren, Y., Rong, K., & Zhou, J. (2021). Women's empowerment in agriculture and household food insecurity: Evidence from Azad Jammu & Kashmir (AJK), Pakistan. *Land Use Policy*, 102, 105249.

Barau, A., & Oladeji, D. O. (2017). Participation of urban women in agricultural production activities in the Sokoto Metropolis, Nigeria. *Journal of Natural Resources and Development*, 7(1), 84-90.

Callister, L. C. (2018). Reducing hunger among women and children in India. *MCN: The American Journal of Maternal/Child Nursing*, 43(4), 234.

- Chigbu, U. E. (2013). Rurality as a choice: Towards ruralizing rural areas in sub-Saharan African countries. *Development Southern Africa*, 30(6), 812-825.
- Chigbu, U. E., Paradza, G., & Dachaga, W. (2019). Differentiations in women's land tenure experiences: implications for women's land access and tenure security in sub-Saharan Africa. *Land*, 8(2), 22-28
- Daramola, C. F., Adebo, T. I., & Adebo, G. M. (2016). Challenges and information need assessment of dry season vegetable farmers in Akure metropolis, Ondo State. *IOSR Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Science Ver. I*, 9(4), 2319 -2372.
- Doss, C. (2014). If women hold up half the sky, how much of the world's food do they produce? In *Gender in agriculture* (69-88). Springer, Dordrecht.
- Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO, 2106). Forest and Agriculture: land use challenges and opportunities. Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i5588e.pdf> on September 25, 2019
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (2017): Gender and land statistics. Retrieved on October 16, 2019 from <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i5488e.pdf>
- Food and Agriculture Organization. (2017). The food Security and Nutrition- Conflict Nexus: *Building Resilience for Food Security, Nutrition and Peace*.
- Gavrilovic, M., Koechlein, E., Kaaria, S., & Winder-Rossi, N. (2018). Gender Perspectives in Social Protection for Rural and Agriculture-dependent Communities.
- George, T. O., Olokoyo, F. O., Osabuohien, E. S., Efobi, U., & Beecroft, I. (2015). Women's access to land and economic empowerment in selected Nigerian communities. In *Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in Retrospect* (45-61). Springer, Cham.
- Ibidapo, I., Oso, O., & Ogunsipe, M. H. (2017). Contributions of Non-Farm Activities in Combating Rural Unemployment in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Greener Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 7(7), 175-181.
- Issoufou, M., Amadou, O., Lawali, D., Saidou, O. M., Habibou, I., & Boubacar, Y. (2020). Constraints and strategies for women's access to land in the regions of Maradi and Zinder (Niger). *Cogent Social Sciences*, 6(1), 1712156 - 1712160
- Kaaria, S., Osorio, M., Wagner, S., & Gallina, A. (2016). Rural women's participation in producer organizations: An analysis of the barriers that women face and strategies to foster equitable and effective participation. *Journal of Gender, Agriculture and Food Security (Agri-Gender)*, 1(302-2016-4754), 148-167.
- Kabir, M. R., Ghosh, S., & Shawly, A. (2019). Causes of Early Marriage and Its Effect on Reproductive Health of Young Mothers in Bangladesh. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 16 (9), 289-297.

Lokonon, B. O. K., & Pilo, M. (2021). Women's access to and control over land and the food security of farming households in rural Benin. *Mondes en development*, (1), 89-107.

Meinzen-Dick, R., Quisumbing, A., Doss, C., & Theis, S. (2019). Women's land rights as a pathway to poverty reduction: Framework and review of available evidence. *Agricultural Systems*, 172, 72-82.

Ntenda, P. A. M. (2019). Association of low birth weight with under nutrition in preschool-aged children in Malawi. *Nutrition journal*, 18(1), 1-15.

Ogunlela, Y. I. and A. A. Mukhtar. (2009). Gender issues in agriculture and rural development in Nigeria: The role of women. *Humanity and Social Sciences Journal* 4 (1), 19-30

Oluwatayo, I. B., Omowunmi, T., & Ojo, A. O. (2019). Land acquisition and use in Nigeria: Implications for sustainable food and livelihood security. *Land Use: Assessing the past, envisioning the future*, edited by LC Loures, 91-110.

Otekhile, C. A., & Verter, N. (2017). The socioeconomic characteristics of rural farmers and their net income in Ojo and Badagry Local Government Areas of Lagos State, Nigeria. *Acta Univ. Agric. Silvic. Mendelianae Brun*, 65, 2037-2043.

Save The Children. (2014). State of the World's Mothers 2014: Saving Mothers and Children in Humanitarian Crises. Available online: <https://www.savethechildren.org>. Retrieved on September 23, 2019.

Shaffer, M. (2019). Empowering Women through Land: An Analysis of the Barriers in Accessing Land Rights within Kisumu County, Kenya.

Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (SIDA, 2015). Women and Food Security.

Udoh, E. J., Akpan, S. B., & Uko, E. F. (2017). Assessment of sustainable livelihood assets of farming households in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 10(4), 83-96.

United States Agency for International Development (USAID). (2015) Muslim Women in Agricultural Education and the Labor Force, University of Florida USAID/BFS/ARP-Funded project Retrieved from:

Westholm, L., & Ostwald, M. (2020). Food production and gender relations in multifunctional landscapes: a literature review. *Agroforestry Systems*, 1-16.

World Bank Report (2018). Unrealized Potential: The High Cost of Gender Inequality in Earnings